

INFLUENCE OF MONTMORILLONITE NANOCCLAY, GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS AND COMBINED NANOCCLAY/GRAPHENE HYBRID ON PROPERTIES OF EPOXY COMPOSITE

Alfred Tcherbi-Narteh¹, Md. Nuruddin¹, Mahesh Hosur¹, Raju Gupta¹, Allyson Lattimore¹, Shaik Jeelani¹

¹Department of Material Science, Tuskegee University
100 Chappie James Center, Tuskegee - Alabama, USA

Email: atcherbi-narteh@mytu.tuskegee.edu web page: <http://www.tuskegee.edu>

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tuskegee University
100 Chappie James Center, Tuskegee - Alabama, USA

Email: mnuruddin2581@mytu.tuskegee.edu, web page: <http://www.tuskegee.edu>

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tuskegee University
100 Chappie James Center, Tuskegee - Alabama, USA

Email: hosur@mytu.tuskegee.edu, web page: <http://www.tuskegee.edu>

Keywords: Graphene Nanoplatelets, Montmorillonite Nanoclay, Binary Nanoparticles

ABSTRACT

In the current work, a comparative study of the influence of 3 wt. % montmorillonite nanoclay Nanomer[®] I.30E (MMT), 0.2 wt. % graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) and two binary systems; (a) 3 wt. % MMT and 0.1 wt. % GNP; and (b) 3 wt. % MMT and 0.2 wt. % GNP on mechanical and viscoelastic properties, and thermal stability of SC-780 epoxy resin composite was investigated. Epoxy SC-780, a two-part diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) resin system, was modified with silane functionalized GNP and octadecylamine modified MMT. Mechanical and viscoelastic properties were characterized using three-point flexure test and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) respectively and compared to that of unmodified composite counterpart. X-ray diffraction studies conducted to investigate the dispersion of MMT, GNP and binary systems in epoxy resin nanocomposites showed good dispersion, leading to significant enhancement in material properties. Flexural strength and modulus increased by 14, 30, 40 and 29%; and, 40, 129, 146 and 150% for 0.2 wt. % GNP, 3 wt. % MMT, and binary systems (a) and (b) infused composite samples respectively. Similarly, storage modulus also increased by 7, 15, 16 and 8% in the order stated above respectively. On the other hand, there were no significant changes in glass transition temperature in all nanocomposites compared to unmodified control system. All nanocomposites showed enhanced thermal stability compared to unmodified epoxy composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Properties of polymeric composites are continually being enhanced by incorporating small amounts of different nanoparticles resulting in improved mechanical, thermal, electrical and viscoelastic properties [1-4]. Other property enhancements include durability of polymeric composites through minimization of detrimental effects of service and environmental factors over time [2,5]. Developments of binary or hybrid nanoparticles systems where two or more nanoparticles are simultaneously or sequentially mixed together in a polymer system are gaining traction due to remarkable results of enhancements in various properties of the composites [6-9]. Thus harnessing desirable properties of each nanoparticle and resulting in composites with multi-functionality. Graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) and montmorillonite nanoclays (MMT) are both two dimensional nanoparticles with dimensions a few nanometers between the platelets. These nanoparticles have high aspect ratio, and widely used as nanofillers in polymeric composites. Their attractiveness is related to the various material property enhancements reported in literature [2-6]. Morphology of these nanoparticles once infused in epoxy resins results in relatively low shear resistance to flow leading to

desirable application such as in structural adhesives [2,10]. On the other hand, this behavior may cause delay in gelation and subsequent formation of viscoelastic properties during curing in composite fabrications. This is due to changes that occur in the chemistry of the polymer systems caused by the interaction of these nanoparticles and polymer molecules, thus influencing rheological, cure behavior and viscoelastic properties of the final composite [5].

Properties of graphene infused epoxy composites have shown significant improvements in their mechanical properties along with viscoelastic, thermal and electrical conductivity [2,5,7]. With these property enhancements, graphene nanoparticles have received significant research attention and currently used widely in several applications, particularly in electronics and as reinforcements in matrix for structural applications [1,2,7]. Significant work has also been reported in literature about the various benefits of using different nanoclay, with diverse outcomes based on the polymer system and type of nanoclay [3,5]. Another important reason for their wide usage is cost and relative ease of processing. Graphene nanoparticles are also relatively cheaper compared to other nanoparticles from carbon derivative such as carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers and nanorods. However, processing of graphene can pose significant challenges due to interlayer attraction caused by large van der Waal forces and strong π - π interactions. This results in high tendency of agglomeration during dispersion and dismal property enhancements. Montmorillonite nanoclay, for similar reasons leads to the formation of flocculated, intercalated and exfoliation microstructure based on the degree of dispersion [3].

Generally, harnessing properties of nanoparticles infused into polymer nanocomposites are determined by factors such as type, concentration chemical compatibility and degree of dispersion, exposing large surface area of the nanoparticles [7]. With recent demand for advanced polymeric materials with multiple functionalities, there is a great deal of interests in harnessing properties of two or more different nanoparticles otherwise called binary or hybrid nanoparticles infused into polymers for targeted applications [6,7]. Due to chemistry and interaction between these nanoparticles and host polymer, it is important to understand and optimize the targeted properties to harness by using appropriate concentration combinations and polymer system. Hence in the current study, SC-780 epoxy polymeric nanocomposites were fabricated using 3 wt. % MMT, 0.2 wt. % GNP and hybrid nanocomposites of 3 wt. % MMT combined with (a) 0.1 and (b) 0.2 wt. % GNP respectively. Mechanical and viscoelastic properties along with thermal stability were investigated and compared to that of neat unmodified SC-780 epoxy composite.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Material

Samples used for this study were fabricated using two part diglycyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin SC-780, infused with 3 wt. % MMT, 0.2 wt. % GNP and binary nanoparticles respectively, to form various nanocomposites and neat SC-780 epoxy composite. Epoxy SC-780 resin was purchased from Applied Poleramic Inc. (USA), while MMT and GNP were purchased from Sigma Aldrich[®] and ACS Material[®] (USA) respectively. Surface of MMT sold under the trade name Nanomer[®] I.30E has been modified with 20–35 wt. % octadecylamine with average particle size between 10–12 nm. Fig. 1 shows graphical representation of GNP and MMT nanoparticles.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of (a) graphene nanoplatelets and (b) montmorillonite nanoclay

Other chemicals used in the study were silane coupling agent, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane, 99.8% anhydrous methanol, acetic acid, ACS reagent, ≥ 99.7 and acetone, all purchased from Sigma Aldrich. As received graphene nanoplatelets were functionalized using silane to enhance chemical bonding between with the resin, while reducing the tendency for agglomeration during dispersion.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Functionalization of GNP was performed by mixing/reacting 1 wt. % silane coupling agent based on measured amount of as received GNP. A solution of 80/20 v/v ethanol/water was prepared followed by the addition of measured GNPs and thoroughly mixed. 1% acetic acid was then added drop-wise to the mixture to maintain a pH level of 3.5 and magnetically stirred at 500 rpm for 90 minutes at room temperature. At the end of the reaction time, GNP suspensions were repeatedly centrifuged, washed with distilled water until pH of 6 and dried at 60°C for 6 hours in a conventional oven.

Measured amount on MMT was added to a beaker with required amount of SC-780 epoxy resin part A, manually stirred and ultra-sonicated for 30 minutes. Parameters used were 30s on 20s off while maintaining the temperature of the mixture at 60°C using antifreeze cooling bath. Post sonicated mixture was stirred using magnetic stirring for 3 hours at 600 rpm and 60°C. Epoxy resin part B measured at 100:27 mixing ratio of part A and B by weight was added, mechanically stirring using high speed stirrer, degassed and poured into molds to fabricate 3 wt. % MMT samples. For GNP and binary nanoparticle samples, identical processing technique was used in addition to three-roll shear mixing to ensure good dispersion of GNP contents. Similarly, measured amounts of part B were added, stirred and degassed to form 0.2 wt. % GNP and binary nanoparticle infused nanocomposites. Neat samples were fabricated by mixing stoichiometric ratio of part A and B, mechanically stirred, degassed and poured into molds, and allowed to cure at 50°C followed by post-curing at 120°C for 3 hours. Samples with 3 wt. % MMT + 0.1 wt. % GNP and 3 wt. % MMT + 0.2 wt. % GNP are denoted Binary A and B respectively.

2.3 Characterization

2.3.1 Microstructural Analysis

Morphology of the various nanocomposites was studied using X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique, where diffraction peaks were obtained for each nanoparticle and compared to those from their respective nanocomposites. Rigaku DMAX - 2000 was used in the study equipped with Cu K α with wavelength $\lambda = 1.54$ nm and operated at 40 kV and 30mA. Each particle and their respective polymer nanocomposite samples were scanned at 0.2° from 2 θ values between 2 - 40°.

2.3.2. Mechanical Characterization

Effects of each nanoparticle contents on the mechanical properties of SC-780 composite were characterized using three-point bending flexure test. Samples were prepared and tested according ASTM 790-10, maintaining span length-to-width ratio of 16:1. Tests were carried out in displacement mode at crosshead speed of 2.0 mm/min. Five samples were tested from each sample batch and average values compared to that of neat SC-780 composite.

2.3.4 Viscoelastic Characterization

Viscoelastic properties of each nanocomposite sample were characterized using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and compared to neat SC-780 epoxy composite. TA Instruments' Q-800 was used in this study and operated in dual cantilever mode at frequency of 1 Hz and amplitude of 15 μ m. Samples were prepared and tested according to ASTM D 4065-06 and scanned at 5°C/min from 30 - 180°C.

2.3.5 Thermal Stability

Thermal stability of SC-780 composites infused with various nanoparticles including binary systems was studied using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). TA Instruments' Q-500 was used, where samples were scanned from 30 - 800°C at a rate of 10°C/min in a dry nitrogen environment at a flow rate of 90 and 10mL for equipment and sample purging. Sample weights throughout TGA scanning were maintained between 13 - 15 mg. Influence of various nanoparticles including binary on decomposition and thermal stability was studied.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural Analysis

Properties of nanoparticle infused polymer composites are generally correlated with compatibility and degree of dispersion within the parent polymer system. Degree of dispersion of these nanoparticles results in exposure of large interfacial area of the nanoparticles within SC-780 epoxy resin, and was studied using X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique utilizing Bragg's Law. Degree of dispersion was measured by the disorderliness of the stacking arrangements of these sheet-like nanoparticles by percolation of epoxy molecules between their layers. This leads to the opening of the intergallery d -spacing of each nanoparticles in their respective nanocomposites compared to the respective d -spacing of each nanoparticle. Fig. 2 shows results from XRD studies from which intensities of diffraction in each nanoparticle including binary systems were compared and was significantly reduced in their respective nanocomposites.

Figure 2. XRD diffraction of (a) graphene, (b) montmorillonite nanoclay and (c) binary nanoparticle and their respective nanocomposites

Relatively lower intensities and broader peaks observed in the diffraction patterns of all nanocomposites are indicative of intercalation. Thus, distortion in the stacking of the nanosheets in both GNP and MMT nanoparticles were caused by percolation of epoxy molecules into the intergallery spacing between the nanoplatelets in the polymer composites compared to their powdered samples.

3.1 Mechanical Characterization

Influence of various nanoparticles on mechanical property of SC-780 nanocomposites was characterized using three point bending flexure test. Flexure strength and modulus of each composite including neat was determined using Zwick Roell Z25 with typical sample dimension of 100mm x 12mm x 5mm in length, width and thickness respectively. Representative curves from the test are shown in Fig. 3 with average data presented in Table 1. Parameters evaluated from the test results were modulus of elasticity and strength for each composite sample. Although mechanical properties of graphene nanoparticles have been noted to be very high [11], 0.2 wt. % used in the study showed enhancements of 14 and 40% for flexural strength and modulus respectively compared to neat unmodified epoxy composite. On the other hand samples with 3 wt. % MMT showed approximately 31 and 129% enhancements in strength and modulus respectively. This shows that GNP interaction with SC-780 epoxy molecules led to relative poor performance compared to MMT and binary nanoparticles infused samples. A strong synergy was observed between 3 wt. % MMT and 0.1 wt. % GNP resulting in stronger interfacial interaction leading to approximately 40% and over 140% increase in the same order mentioned above compared to unmodified neat SC-780 epoxy composite.

Figure 3. Representative flexural stress-strain curves

Table 1. Summary of Flexural Properties of Neat SC-780 and Nanocomposites

Samples	Flexural Strength, MPa	% Change	Flexural Modulus, GPa	% Change
Neat	79.90±1.97	–	1.29±0.03	–
0.2 wt.% GNP	91.24±1.83	14.19	1.81±0.08	40.31
3 wt. % MMT	105.34±2.03	31.84	2.96±0.03	129.46
Binary A	111.53±1.79	39.59	3.17±0.08	145.74
Binary B	102.67±2.19	28.50	3.22±0.09	149.61

As GNP content increased from 0.1 wt. % to 0.2 wt. % in the binary system, there was a slight decrease of about 10% in strength and a 5% increase in modulus compared to the previous. The decrease however was significant when compared to unmodified samples, thus an improvement of about 28% and 149% respectively. This indicates that optimum loading combination where chemical interactions between all components gave rise to best mechanical properties was 3 wt. % MMT and 0.1 wt. % GNP. Improvements in mechanical properties were also attributed to high aspect ratios of the various nanoparticles used as nanofillers in this study [11,12].

3.2 Viscoelastic Characterization

Characterization of viscoelastic properties of SC-780 epoxy composites infused with different nanoparticles was done using dynamic mechanical analysis. Parameters determined from this test were storage modulus and glass transition temperature (T_g). Several reports in literature have indicated that interactions between nanofillers and epoxy resins results in improvements in glass transition temperatures and storage modulus [13]. This is generally attributed to polymer chains trapped within the filler network causing resistive mobility, hence enhancements in material properties including thermal [14,15]. However, results from the study showed improvements in storage modulus and statistically no changes in glass transition temperatures. Representative curves obtained from dynamic mechanical analysis tests are shown in Fig. 4 and average results in Table 2. As expected, composition and surface functionalization of each nanoparticle including binary systems interacted differently with the epoxy molecules leading to disproportionate amounts of epoxy molecules percolating into the layers of each nanoparticle. The result of which showed different improvements in storage modulus with 3 wt. % MMT and binary system consisting of 3 wt. % and 0.1 wt. % GNP showing to most enhancements. Glass transition temperature determined from the peak of loss moduli curves showed insignificant enhancements as also reported by Stanier et al. [13]. They attributed the lack of enhancement to lower quantity of fluidified polymer molecules available during glass transition.

Figure 4. Representative storage modulus curves for all samples

Table 2. Summary of Viscoelastic Properties of Neat SC-780 and Nanocomposites

Samples	Storage Modulus, MPa	% Change	Glass Transition Temperature, °C	% Change
Neat	2397±233	–	94.98±4.98	–
0.2 wt.% GNP	2554±89	6.55	96.94±2.79	2.06
3 wt. % MMT	2758±138	15.06	94.93±0.30	-0.05
Binary A	2795±115	16.60	95.18±4.46	0.21
Binary B	2597±80	8.34	94.36±1.38	-0.65

Morphologies of these nanoparticles however have been shown to influence resistance to flow hence at glass transition restrictive segmental movement of entrapped epoxy molecules was offset by the presence and effect of nanoparticle morphology resulting in a net zero effect. Consequently leading to no changes in T_g as observed in the study. Such behavior has been reported with single and multi-walled carbon nanotubes and other forms of carbon black [6,13].

3.3 Thermal Stability

Thermal stability, barrier and flame retardancy properties of MMT and GNP have been attributed to their inherent sheet-like nature. Interactions of various nanoparticles and epoxy molecules on thermal stability of their respective nanocomposites were investigated using thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA). Although thermal stability improvements have been reported with the addition of graphene [2,6] and nanoclay [14], results of the study showed insignificant changes in both onset and decomposition temperatures shown in Table 3. On the other hand, char formation at 650°C increased in all nano-infused samples. Physical characteristics and rate of formation of char dictates the rate of further decomposition of the remaining polymer composites as temperature increases. Hence results of TGA studies particular char yield highlights improvements in thermal stability of nanoparticle infused samples compared to unmodified epoxy samples, with binary systems showing higher char content, followed by MMT.

Table 3. Summary of TGA Results of Neat SC-780 and Nanocomposites

Samples	Onset of Decomp. T ₅ , °C	% Change	Decomp Temp. T _p , °C	% Change	Residue %	% Change
Neat	302.80±4.1		314.91±4.4		10.61±0.8	
0.2 wt.% GNP	299.56±2.4	-1.07	313.08±5.8	-0.58	11.45±0.5	7.92
3 wt. % MMT	295.46±1.9	-2.42	306.77±7.2	-2.58	12.17±1.0	14.70
Binary A	297.10±2.2	-1.88	312.28±3.3	-0.84	12.43±0.6	17.15
Binary B	295.41±3.1	-2.44	312.69±5.9	-0.70	12.85±1.4	21.11

4 CONCLUSIONS

Influence of MMT, GNP and combination of the two nanoparticles on properties of epoxy SC-780 was investigated. Results of the study showed a strong synergy between 3 wt. % MMT and 0.1 wt. % on SC-780 leading to most property enhancements in mechanical properties. Significant flexural modulus was observed with binary and MMT infused samples with the least enhancement observed in 0.2 wt. % GNP samples. Storage modulus increased in all nano-infused samples with Binary A showing the most improvement of about 16%. On the other hand, addition of nanoparticles did not enhance glass transition temperature. TGA studies also showed improvement in char formation in all nanocomposites samples compared to unmodified SC-780 composite, indicative of enhanced thermal stability, with statistically insignificant changes in onset and decomposition temperatures. Optimum loading of MMT and GNP combination was observed to be 3 wt. % MMT and 0.1 wt. % GNP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge NSF EPSCoR support through Grant number 111583 and the Alabama Commission on Higher Education (ACHE) for funding this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Sengupta, M. Bhattacharya, S. Bandyopadhyay, A. K. Bhowmick, A review on the mechanical and electrical properties of graphite and modified graphite reinforced polymer composites. *Progress in Polymer Science*, **36**, 2011, pp. 638–670.
- [2] T. Kuilla, S. Bhadra, D. Yao, N. H. Kim, S. Bose, J. H. Lee, Recent advances in graphene based polymer composites. *Progress in Polymer Science*, **35**, 2010, pp. 1350–1375.
- [3] S. Sinha Ray, M. Okamoto, Polymer/layered silicate nanocomposites: a review from preparation to processing, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **28**, 2003, pp. 1539–1641.
- [4] D. Zhuo, R. Wang, L. Wu, Y. Guo, L. Ma, Z. Weng, and J. Qi, Flame retardancy effects of graphene nanoplatelet/carbon nanotube hybrid membranes on carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, vol. 2013, Article ID 820901, pp. 1-7, ([doi:10.1155/2013/820901](https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/820901))
- [5] A. Tcherbi-Narteh, M. Hosur, E. Triggs, P. Owuor, S. Jeelani, Viscoelastic and thermal properties of full and partially cured DGEBA epoxy resin composites modified with montmorillonite nanoclay exposed to UV radiation, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **101**, 2014, pp. 81-91.
- [6] S-Y. Yang, W-N. Lin, Y-L. Huang, H-W. Tien, J-Y. Wang, C-C. M. Ma, S-M. Li, Y.-S. Wang. Synergetic effects of graphene platelets and carbon nanotubes on the mechanical and thermal properties of epoxy composites, *CARBON*, **49**, 2011, pp. 793–803.
- [7] S. Zhang, S. Yin, C. Rong, P. Huo, Z. Jiang, G. Wang, Synergistic effects of functionalized graphene and functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes on the electrical and mechanical properties of poly(ether sulfone) composites, *European Polymer Journal*, **49**, 2013, pp. 3125–3134.
- [8] M.M. Shokrieh, M. Esmkhani, A.R. Haghightakhah, Z. Zhao, Flexural fatigue behavior of synthesized graphene/carbon-nanofiber/epoxy hybrid nanocomposites, *Materials and Design*, **62**, 2014, pp. 401–408.
- [9] W. Li, A. Dichiara, J. Bai, Carbon nanotube–graphene nanoplatelet hybrids as high-performance multifunctional reinforcements in epoxy composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **74**, 2013, pp. 221–227.
- [10] S. Pradhan, P. K. Guchhait, K. D. Kumar and A. K. Bhowmick, Influence of Nanoclay on the Adhesive and Physico-Mechanical Properties of Liquid Polysulfide Elastomer. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. **23**, (16), 2009, pp. 2013-2029.
- [11] C. Lee, X. Wei, J. W. Kysar, J. Hone, Measurement of the elastic properties and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene. *Science*, **321**, 2008, pp. 385–388.
- [12] A. S. Wajid, H. S. T. Ahmed, S. Das, F. Irin, A.F. Jankowski, M. J. Green, High- performance pristine graphene/epoxy composites with enhanced mechanical and electrical properties, *Macromolecular Materials Engineering*, **298**, 2013, pp. 339–347.
- [13] D. C. Stanier, A. J. Patil, C. Sriwong, S. S. Rahatekar, J. Ciambella, The reinforcement effect of exfoliated graphene oxide nanoplatelets on the mechanical and viscoelastic properties of natural rubber. *Composites Science and Technology*, **95**, 2014, pp. 59–66.
- [14] M. S. Lakshmi, B. Narmadha, B. S. R. Reddy, Enhanced thermal stability and structural characteristics of different MMT-Clay/epoxy-nanocomposite materials, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **93**, 2008, pp. 201–213.
- [15] B. Tang, G. Hu, H. Gao, L. Hai, Application of graphene as filler to improve thermal transport property of epoxy resin for thermal interface materials, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, **85**, 2015, pp. 420–429.